

THE USE OF ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY AND EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the structure and experience of the advanced foreign education system, such as Japan, France, the United States, and recognizes the achievements of the New Uzbekistan in the current educational system.*

Keywords: *education, foreign experience, structure, International Assessment, country, educational inspection, intellectual.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ПЕРЕДОВОГО ЗАРУБЕЖНОГО ОПЫТА В ПОВЫШЕНИИ КАЧЕСТВА И ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В этой статье анализируется структура и опыт передовых зарубежных систем образования, таких как Япония, Франция, США, а также признаются достижения нового Узбекистана в современной системе образования.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, зарубежный опыт, структура, международная оценка, страна, инспекция образования, интеллектуальная.*

Our country has implemented and continues to carry out a complex process of comprehensive reforms and reconstruction in the educational system. It should be taken into account that the changes taking place in our society in the economic-social, political, cultural spheres also depend on the educational system, which in the future determines the intellectual capabilities of our country and is considered the main condition for its development.

Understanding the need for reform of the educational system makes it necessary in practice to integrate educational institutions into innovative processes. Education, which is currently being updated and developing, means a new thought and healthy thinking in the full sense of the system.

Nowadays, the value and prestige of education is increasing. On an equal footing, self-sacrifice and bold enthusiasm should also be present in its performers. Development in education will be by those who act boldly. Shijoat, on the other hand, can be enlightened by school science, as noted by the Uzbek classical figure Abdullah Avlani. From time immemorial, knowledge was

appreciated in the countries of the East, including US. And the people of Ilm Marifat were in the land of Arda. thanks to this, it is our high duty to acquire knowledge and serve the acquired knowledge in the way of the development of our country. One of the ways to solve these tasks is to study the experiences of a foreign school and pedagogy.

By studying international advanced foreign methodologies, we will get rid of traditional forms in education and training, as well as a methodology that complies with international standards, the result of which is guaranteed.

Modern educational institutions such as presidential schools, schools of creativity and specialized schools named after our great-grandfathers were established. It offers classes through international and modern methodologies. This is a sign that mature cadres will mature in the future.

In accordance with the resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on November 26, 2019 on measures to establish "modern schools", the main task was to convert at least 3% of schoolchildren to "modern schools" by 2021, 20% to 2025, and 50% to "modern schools" by 2030.

In our country, only 10 percent of the practical classes of Applied Sciences, namely Mathematics, Chemistry, Physics and biology, are allocated to practical classes. And in developed countries, this figure is 30-50 percent.

Therefore, the Ministry of public education of the Ministry of development of information technologies and communiqés is tasked with making extensive use of digital technologies in training programs, and increasing the scope of practical training in the Exact Sciences.

Today, the emphasis on education is increasing in every country. Below we list information about the educational system of developed countries:

Japanese education system. Japanese education is special among developed countries. In particular, the structure of the Japanese educational system is as follows: preschool, elementary school, Junior High School, Upper Secondary School, higher education institutions that are part of higher education systems. In the Japanese education system, primary education teachers teach a child to think freely as well as to be able to criticize. Japan is the only state within developed countries where the teacher's salary is higher among heads of state. In the Japanese educational system, together with the school, the family also plays an important role in the upbringing of the child. Especially the role and responsibility of mothers is great. Mothers consider themselves responsible to the state so that their children can hang out smart and hardworking.

In Japan, not only the national traditions are limited, but also the pedagogical work-experiments of such progressive countries as the United States, France, Germany in the world are creatively mastered.

United States education system. Secondary education in America is 12 years, divided into primary secondary and lower schools. In this state, schools do not have numbers, but they are called by huuds or by the name of famous people. Usually every classroom has computers and televisions. Computer classes, on the other hand, are connected to yiuqori speed internet.

Elementary school mathematics is somewhat more lightly structured compared to other states. For example, the multiplication table starts with Grade 3. One of the great ways in the American education system is to run an account card for each student. In it, each student is 10 different assessed by behavior. Parents who see this card try to fix it by looking at the negative aspects of their children.

As a conclusion, it is worth noting that any innovations, changes, serious analyzes enter education on the basis of experiences. Uzbekistan was scheduled to participate in the International Assessment System of PISA and PIRLS in 2021. This test was attended by students of the 4th grade of our country. This made it possible to study and practice the international experiences of developed countries participating in the International Assessment System in order to prepare students for this process.

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